

COMPUTER SCIENCES

INTEGRATED ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AS A MEANS OF OPTIMIZING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN THE CONDITIONS OF DISTANCE EDUCATION

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Abstract

The proposed article emphasizes the need to actively introduce the latest distance education technologies into the educational process, including those involving artificial intelligence. The developed system of distance education is described, which allows improving the educational process and increasing the convenience of the educational process for scientific and pedagogical workers and students of higher education through integration into the artificial intelligence system for creating tests. The developed system has a unique innovative functionality that allows you to easily create tests automatically using artificial intelligence.

Keywords: educational process, distance learning, computer system, artificial intelligence, design, modeling.

Introduction. Since the 90s of the last centuries, the world scientific and pedagogical community has been actively raising the issue of using alternative forms of educational activity, such as: distance learning, mediated learning, online learning, etc., which have gained special importance in connection with the development of the Internet [1–18].

Today's challenges require the scientific and pedagogical worker to transform not only the methods and techniques of teaching in higher education, but also the transition to a completely unusual mode of work using online platforms in the educational process. Moreover, it is not only about online education as a component of the educational process, but about the complete replacement of traditional education with online learning.

These issues have become especially relevant in 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic and developed during the war.

The main tools of the educational process in general and higher education in particular have become online services that provide the possibility of posting educational materials, organizing video meetings, conducting current and final examinations and keeping an assessment log. Google Classroom, Microsoft 365 and virtual educational spaces of universities based on the Moodle platform have become the main online platforms for the organization of e-learning in Ukrainian institutions of higher education, each of which has its own advantages and disadvantages [9].

Therefore, modern didactic science actively directs its developments in the direction of improving the available tools of online education.

The proposed study is devoted to the creation of a prototype system for distance learning. The developed system will be distributed under the name Educational Site, which fully reflects its main content.

Results. In the process of designing a software tool, it is not always possible to predict all aspects, so inaccuracies may appear during the creation of a prototype. This provides an opportunity to supplement the existing description with new information and get rid of them when creating a full-fledged system.

In the system under development, input data is filled by all participants, because they have special interfaces through which they enter information. For example, a teacher can create a test manually or using artificial intelligence, which will be transferred to the database, and then stored in tables, following the rules of normalization. During the test, the student will be able to view this data, which will be displayed after processing by the backend. The proposed system is based on the principle of client-server technology, which involves data exchange between the client and the server. From this follows the need for a high-quality Internet connection for the program to work.

When the user enters the site for the first time, the main page of the site opens, where the list of available courses is displayed in the foreground. In the left part there is a navigation menu with two buttons: authorization and registration, they are used to redirect to pages that will have their own forms. In order to enter the site, you need to register. After registering and authorizing according to the role, a navigation box will be displayed.

A navigation field with links to pages will be available for the student:

- view of the course, where links are presented, with the help of which joining to online lectures, laboratory works or review of theoretical material is performed;
- view the schedule, which is displayed for the whole week and is available for viewing, providing information about the schedule of classes;
- passing the test, where there is an opportunity to check your knowledge by running the test, in which the questions are displayed one by one, and after the test is completed, the final grade is shown;
- viewing the list of courses, he is studying.

For this role, the home page will show a list of courses the student is attached to, and navigating to each course will display a list of tutorials and tests that can be taken.

The following will be displayed for the teacher:

- creating a course on which fields with the following names are available: name, description;
- viewing the schedule, where it is possible to view the schedule of groups for a week, which provides a complete overview of the schedule of the educational process;
- review of grades, where you can view grades received by students after testing;
- creating a test, in addition, it is possible to create tests manually or generate them using AI.

On the main page, the teacher is presented with a list of courses to which he has joined. When switching to any course created by him, a functionality will be available where he will be able to add educational material, invite to an online lecture or create a test.

University departments have the following opportunity:

- creating a schedule, where you can create a schedule by adding information according to groups;
- group management, which contains information about all groups, as well as options for editing, deleting or adding new ones;
- course management, where you can manage courses, including creating, editing and deleting.

All pages are available to the administrator, as well as:

- editing, where it is possible to change all the information stored in the database: group, student, teacher, subject, schedule, etc. d. The ability to edit, add and delete, which provides full control over information in the system.

The administrator has full access to all functionality, including those that are closed to regular users.

The system must be ready to increase users and process a significant number of requests in a short period of time. As the audience increases, the amount of stored information also increases. With proper design, the stability and speed of the system should be ensured when the load increases.

In order to save memory and speed in the future at the stage of database design, it must be normalized, because the tables should not contain duplicate data, and since all the relationships between them are interconnected, when you delete a course, the related to it will be automatically deleted records.

The backend is responsible for managing the database, which is influenced by the frontend. That is, the database does not necessarily have to be on the same server, but if it is, then the speed of requests will be longer by a few hundredths of a second.

For secure communication between the frontend and the backend, a special key is added to the requests, which is automatically generated after each authorization and is used as a user identification when contacting the server, which ensures a high level of reliability and reduces the probability of unauthorized access.

The server must have the functionality to regularly back up data. This is necessary so that in the event of a fatal error there is an opportunity to restore the integrity of the data and avoid its loss.

It is also necessary to pay close attention to the user's data, which he enters during registration, in particular, his password. Security is ensured by storing the password in encrypted form. This is an important measure designed to ensure that in the event of a database breach, no one can access user data.

System modeling is one of the most important stages in software design. At this stage, an analysis of how the future product will be used is carried out, with a detailed description of the actions. This section also defines all users (actors) and the actions they will perform (precedents).

The construction of these diagrams is performed using a special modeling language – UML. This language was chosen due to the fact that it is standardized, and the scheme described by the rules will be understood by anyone who works with it.

The output of the proposed modeling will be using case and sequence diagrams. Based on the obtained results, you can move on to designing the architecture of the software tool and its implementation.

Let's first describe the system being developed at a conceptual level with the help of a use case diagram. It will allow to display the interaction of entities and actors of the project with precedents.

The following elements of the system can be distinguished:

- users: administrator, department employees, student, teacher, and to make it more convenient, another "user" actor was created, which will combine a department employee, student, and teacher. Also in the diagram is a "system" actor that accepts requests from others;
- precedents: login to the system, CRUD operations on data, view grades, view schedule, course management, subject management, course study.

Let's move on to a brief description of each precedent:

- login to the system – describes authorization, it also provides for the possibility of registration or displaying an error in case of entering incorrect data;
- CRUD operations on data – describes how the administrator performs work on information: editing, creating and deleting records;
- view ratings – describes how the user can view information related to ratings;
- viewing the schedule – the user can view the schedule of his group;

- course management – describes how a department employee can manage a course, also extended by the ability to manage groups, which are complemented by schedule management;

- subject management – describes how the teacher can manage the subject, which is extended by theory and test management;

- studying the course – describes how the student can study the course, theory and tests.

Sequence diagram – it is used to depict how objects interact in an orderly manner in time and their aspects. With the help of such diagrams, they display the life cycle during which the interaction of an actor with the system is performed within the framework of the current precedent. Its purpose is to display objects in dynamics, information is provided in the form of messages, and interaction involves exchanging them within the scenario.

Before designing a system prototype, you need to choose the right architecture, because the work and existence of the development system depends on it.

Choosing a software architecture is one of the most important roles and is the most important in software development. It contains components, their properties and relationships between them. That is, it describes the principle of organization of components in the system. Documenting this architecture simplifies the communication process, predicts flaws, and makes it possible to reuse templates in other projects. A properly designed architecture can save time and money, as well as increase the speed of the development product.

Currently, the leaders in architecture are monolithic and microservice, so let's consider them in more detail.

Monolithic is an architecture that is developed as a single package, meaning the software will be packaged into a single monolith and deployed in the same way. In the architecture of this type, only one technology is used, due to the fact that the program is assembled in one place, it is easy to add new features to it, and it runs in one place and is autonomous, it has a high speed of exchange between modules, because they are next to each other in the same code and work within the framework of one software tool.

Microservice is an architecture that follows a modular type of development, that is, it consists of independent parts, modules that can be used in different applications, but at the same time they exchange information using methods (interfaces). In this type of architecture, each component is independent and can be implemented in different programming languages.

In the proposed study, the system will be designed according to the architecture of the monolith, because the software tools of this type are easily deployed within the framework of one server, are easily developed and have high performance due to the fact that the components are close to each other within the same code. But the disadvantage of this approach can be that over time the system code is modernized and increased, which in the end can lead to the fact that the code becomes overloaded and difficult for the developer to understand.

For a better understanding of how the program will work on physical equipment, a special deployment diagram is used – a special diagram that shows the components: web servers, database servers, or the application server, as well as how they interact with each other.

The client opens a page using a web browser and sends various commands to the server without even realizing it. Special software is installed on the server, which makes it possible to run a site written in the php programming language, as well as a MySQL database. The client and server communicate using the HTTPS protocol.

When accessed from the client's web browser, it sends special requests to the Laravel application, which receives them and forwards them to the router. After the router has processed this request, it calls a special controller class. This class accepts the entire request and, if necessary, receives data to work with later, or immediately provides a response in the form of JSON code.

These actions are performed according to the rules of the MVC design pattern, because the entire Laravel framework is built according to this pattern. It was created to facilitate the work of developers so that if we decipher this abbreviation, we will get three words “Model-View-Controller”. A model is a class through which any kind of communication with a database is performed, a view is what is displayed to the user, a controller is all business logic.

In more detail, the router calls a controller that is selected from a list of all routes and can interact with the model and perform some business logic. After all interactions, it starts generating a response to the client's web browser in the form of JSON, which is displayed to the user.

For convenient development and editing of Laravel in the file hierarchy models, views and controllers are stored in different directories according to the structure of Laravel.

The main Model manages the entire database, and from it inherits the User Model, Schedule Model and System Model models, which have the main data set they are responsible for. These models are controlled by three controllers: User Controller, Schedule Controller and System Controller, which will work with their data depending on the desired result: creating new records, deleting, editing or displaying them.

Conclusion. Today, online training is used in the preparation of higher education applicants of all specialties. Among its indisputable advantages, the following can be highlighted: long-term strategy; flexibility, democracy, the opportunity to more fully implement the individual educational trajectory of applicants and a student-centered approach to learning; the level of absolute success and the quality of education of higher education applicants does not decrease; helps to overcome barriers and increase the level of ownership of digital technologies; promotes the development of creative and innovative teaching methods, including personalization of the educational process, increasing the level of cooperation both between students and between teachers, lecturers and students, promotes cooperation; provides access to domestic and foreign educational resources, etc.

The presented system contains the following types

of users: student, teacher, department employees and administrator. The student has the right to review existing and subscribed courses, schedules, theoretical materials, and passing tests. The teacher and the employees of the respective departments have the ability to create, modify and delete the data corresponding to their roles. The administrator has full rights and can interact with any data stored in the system.

The developed mathematical model makes it possible to determine that time saving when using artificial intelligence to create a test can reach almost 62.5%, which allows to significantly reduce the teacher's time consumption. With such an opportunity, it is possible to develop tests of various levels of complexity, and this allows to identify gaps in the knowledge of higher education applicants and to effectively adjust the educational process.

An analysis of the subject area was also carried out, the possibilities were clearly delineated and the requirements for users with different roles were described, the main functionality of the system was outlined, and possible easy expansion of the functionality in the future was taken into account.

Before development, various modern tools were analyzed and favorites were chosen, namely: the Laravel framework, the React library, and the ChatGpt service for using artificial intelligence.

A monolithic architecture is chosen, which is best suited for a system of this type.

As a result of the use of these tools, a fully functional distance learning system with the integration of artificial intelligence was implemented, which fully meets the tasks set at the beginning of the project.

After development, comprehensive testing, validation and code minimization were performed in order to improve the weight and loading speed of the site. An experiment with the creation of a test using AI confirmed the effectiveness of the system, which means that the goal of the work has been achieved.

The test implementation of the project on the Internet included the description of instructions for search robots, the activation of indexing in Google search and the use of the semantic core for the selection of keywords in order to improve the search visibility of the site.

The obtained result shows that the system is ready for implementation, meets the set tasks, has the potential for further development, contributes to the optimization of distance learning for students of higher education and scientific and pedagogical workers.

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